

Nepal's Cultural Wealth Meets the Digital Age: Why Digital Anthropology Matters

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Originally published in OnlineKhabar English – August 17, 2025

Full text available at: <https://english.onlinekhabar.com/nepals-cultural-wealth-meets-the-digital-age-why-digital-anthropology-matters.html>

This article examines the intersection of Nepal's cultural heritage and the digital age, introducing digital anthropology as an emerging field in Nepali academia. It discusses how digital technologies and traditional practices are increasingly interwoven in shaping identity, knowledge, and society. Drawing on insights from the International Conference on Anthropology of Nepal and the Himalayas (July 2025), the article emphasizes the importance of integrating digital anthropology into academic, cultural, and policy discussions.